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**A STUDY OF MANAGEMENT PROBLEM IN MULTI GRADE CLASSROOM
MANAGEMENT AT PRIMARY SCHOOL :WITH
REFERENCE TO THE NANDED REGION**

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Introduction:

Education is the basic need in the present era. According to Charles Darwin's theory of "SURVIVAL OF THE FITTEST" the one who are liable to live lives and those who are not capable to live destroys. Education is essential to survive in this era. The good education is important to live better and progressive life. Parents as well as teachers are responsible for giving the better education to pupil.

Pupil progresses faster if he gets the individual observation and guidance in family and school. But many times the student can't get the individual guidance or progressive atmosphere due to many reasons such as the insufficient teachers for all classes, students' large quantity in single class etc. That time teacher has to use many tricks to manage the class and give education to pupil. In these tricks the teacher uses Activity Based Learning, Classroom Teaching, Multi grade Class etc. One teacher teaches two or more than two classes at the same time is called as multiple class and teaching technique of method is called multi grade teaching. And the skill to handle two or more than two classes at the same time is called multi grade class management.

Teacher uses various strategies to manage and control the multi class. There are some strategies as follows:

Class room Management Strategies:

In multi grade class teaching one or more teacher have to manage two or more classes at the same time.

Number of teachers	Teacher 1	Teacher 2	Teacher 3	Teacher 4
1	1,2,3,4	----	----	----
2	1,2	3,4	----	----
3	1	2	3,4	----
4	1	2	3	4

www.priciples.in

Multigrade teaching occurs within a graded system of education when a single class contains two or more student grade levels. It is contrasted with the usual pattern of classroom organization in graded systems where a single classroom contains students of only one grade level. In many graded systems, age and grade are congruent, so a grade level is also equivalent to a particular age group of students. However, this may not be the case in systems where grade level repetition and acceleration are common. There are three important reasons why multigrade teaching may occur in both developed and developing countries.

First, multigrading is often associated with 'small' schools in remote and sparsely populated areas. In such schools, there may be only one, two or three teachers, yet they offer a complete cycle of primary education. If that cycle consists of eight grade levels, then each of these teachers must deal with multigrade classes. These 'small' schools are also sometimes referred to as 'multigrade' schools. Multigrade schools have attracted attention in the developing country context because of their potential to increase primary school participation rates. By bringing the school closer to the community, they encourage more children, especially girls, into school.

Second, multigrade teaching is also common in larger urban and suburban schools. In some countries, it is a response to uneven student enrollment. For example, a school with a two and a half grade entry may have to combine two grade levels to make up class sizes. Also, in countries where teacher absenteeism is high, and there is no 'cover', grades may be combined to avoid having a class with no teacher present. A single teacher then has to deal with two grade level groups together. While the latter problem is not well-documented in the literature, it is probably a regular occurrence in countries in both Africa and the Caribbean.

Third, multigrade teaching may be a deliberate response to educational problems. In developed countries, this is linked to the multiage perspective. Proponents of mixed age grouping argue that there are sound pedagogical reasons for placing students of different ages together in the same classroom. Mixed age classes, it is argued, stimulate children's social development and encourage greater classroom cooperation. These arguments are seldom raised in the developing country literature, although several commentators take the view that

multigrade organized classes are potentially a cost effective means of providing quality education in difficult to reach areas.

<http://www.ioe.ac.uk/multigrade>

It is assumed that teaching takes place in three types of situations.

Situation 1 :

Class 1: By showing pictures, the teacher makes the students express their ideas related to the pictures.

Situation 2 :

Class 2 : The students are asked to sit in pairs. One student talks about his house grade to the other. It is followed by the other students afterwards.

Situation 3 :

Class 3 : The students copy their lessons in their notebook / slate.

In the first situation, the I std students listen to the teacher. The students are made to think.

In the second situation, the II std students express what they feel & whatever is registered in their minds are expressed by them.

In the third situation, children are involved in activities.

In these three situations of Learning, Knowledge, and Register & Motivation' takes place:

In situation - 1, Group teaching takes place.

In situation - 2, Learning takes place in small groups.

In situation - 3, Learning takes place in one group to develop interest in writing, assign writing work to 2 or 3 groups. Conduct competitions on writing.

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Definition Of Terms In Title:

Multi Grade Classroom:

The term multilevel classrooms refers to student centered classrooms in which students learn across two or more grades and are taught by the same teacher for two or more years.

www.edu.gov.mb.ca

Management:

Management is the process of bringing the improvement in knowledge, skills, habits and attitudes of the employees in an organization.

Primary School:

The school having classes 1st to 7th is called primary school.

Objectives Of The Research:

- 1) To study the problems of teacher in multi grade class room management.
- 2) To compare single class room management and multi grade class room management.
- 3) To study the management of multi grade class room management.
- 4) To find out effective management in multi grade class room.
- 5) To study the strategies and techniques of multi grade class room management.

Importance Of The Research:

- 1) It helps to manage two or more than two class.
- 2) It helps to design multiple classroom management strategies.

- 3) It helps to give individual attention to pupil.
- 4) It helps in controlling of students behavior.

Hypothesis Of The Research:

1. There is significant difference between single class room and multi grade class room management.
2. To participate students in management process to get effective multi grade class room management.
3. To take team management process in multi grade class room management to get effective management.
4. To select effective management of related content in multiple class to get objective of teaching.
5. To take co-operative group work in students to get effective class room management.

Scope And Limitation Of The Study:

- 1) This research is limited to area of Mudkhed taluka only.
- 2) This research includes students of class 1-7 in zilla parishad Marathi medium school only.
- 3) This research is limited to area of management in multiple classroom management.
- 4) This research is limited to time and teaching strategies used by teacher in multi grade class management.
- 5) This research is only for the year 2013-2014.

Research Methodology:

Research Methodology is a systematic method of discovering new facts or verifying old facts, their sequence, inter-relationship, casual explanation and the Natural laws which governs them. Research Methodology explained by *Redman* and *Mory* are as follows Systematized effort to gain new knowledge, Research Methodology is original contribution to the existing stock of knowledge, making for its advancement.

In this research the researcher used survey method and evaluate above statement of problem.

Conclusion and Major Findings:

1. Most of the teachers used to combine the similar age groups with respective to the talent level to control the multi grade classes.
2. All of teachers agree that time is properly organized in multi-grade teaching. It is important to distribute time to control the both classes.
3. All of the teachers are of the opinion that the children do self study when the teacher is not with them.
4. All the teachers believe that monitor system is essential for implementation of MGCM.
5. Most of the teachers think that the children of higher class can teach the lower classes but some teachers think that the student from the same class can teach the class.
6. All teachers agree that the children of higher classes help in control over the students of lower classes in their absence.
7. All teachers agree that to control the class is the main reason of combining the class and no one believes in effective teaching to large number of students.
8. Most of teachers try their best to keep all students active but some teachers are not able to do it.
9. In this system it is difficult for teachers to complete the syllabus in the time.
10. Very few teachers can follow the time table because the different classes have the different timetable from one another. In this MGCM system teachers use the flexibility in following the time table.
11. All of the teachers motive students by giving instruction to keep discipline before combining the class.
12. All of the teachers have responded in favors that this method is effective for solving the problems related to the different class management at one time.
13. Most of the teachers agree to solve the problems related to teaching by this technique.
14. Most of the teachers believe that discipline can be maintained in MGCM.

15. Most of the teachers agree that MGCM helped in reducing your burden of teachers. By the effective use of technique like monitorial assistance, self study, peer group etc burden can be reduced to a large number.
16. Most of the teachers agree children concentrate on study. But some students are not concentrating on studies properly due to the large numbers of students in one class.
17. In this system it is difficult for teachers solving the problem of examination results.
18. MGCM is useful in solving the problem of misbehavior of students.
19. Most of the teachers use the teaching learning process in multi grade class management.
20. Most of the teachers believe that the children perform activities in the MGCM situation.
21. Most of the teachers believe that the teachers recapitulate under this system after the lesson is over but some teachers can't recapitulate due to the lack of time and the large number of students.
22. Most of the teachers agree that the problems of children solved by this system.
23. All teachers believe that the class-work and home-work assigned to students under this system.
24. Most of the teachers believe that the teacher can control over the both classes in MGCM but some think it is hard to control the both classes at the same time.
25. Most of the teachers believe that the experimental work is performed in this system but some teachers believe that the experimental work is not performed in this system.
26. Most of the teachers believe that punishment is not necessary to control the students in management of multi grade class.
27. The teacher who uses the punishment to manage the class believes that the only verbal punishment is sufficient to manage the multi grade classes.
28. Most of the students are doing self study, some students are busy with the group work when the teacher is absent in the class.
29. Most of school teachers use the monitors to manage the class.
30. Most of teachers are able to keep discipline in the class.
31. Most of the students of lower class are paying attention while being taught.
32. Teachers frequently use the teaching aids to manage the multi grade classes.
33. Most of the teachers create the groups to manage the class.
34. Most of the teachers cannot recapitulate the lesson due to the lack of time.

35. Most of the students give the answer to teacher while some students busy with elsewhere.
36. Most of the teachers don't use any penalty for misbehavior of students but they give instructions before combining the class.
37. Most of the students are engaged with their work in the multi grade class management.

Recommendation:

Researcher studies this problem and then pens down the recommendations for the teachers how to manage multi grade classrooms.

Recommendation for the Teachers-

1. In Multi Grade Class room Management teachers have to use pre-instructions before combining the multi grade classes.
2. In MCGM teachers have to pay attention on combining the similar or liner classes.
3. In MGCM teachers have to create proper groups in the class.
4. In MGCM teachers have to create monitorial system for the class in their absence.
5. In MGCM teachers have to use teaching aids as possible as they can.
6. In MGCM teachers have to take help of the bright students to maintain discipline in the class.

Recommendations for the Government-

1. The Government has to give separate teachers for every class.
2. The Government has to pay attention on providing sufficient teaching aids so that students will engage with them.
3. The Government has to give teachers in every z.p.schools as per student strength and class.
4. The government has to pay individual attention through senior officers to teacher problems in MGCM.
5. The Government has to give extra increment for those teachers who manage multi grade classes.

Further Studies:

The following topics can be undertaken for the further research.

1. To study the teachers problems in the multi grade class room management at high school level.
2. To study the teachers problems in the multi grade class room management at college level.
3. To observe students in absence of teacher in the multi grade class.
4. A study of student problems in the multi grade class room management at primary school level.
5. A study of teachers problem in the multi grade students management at pre primary level.

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